

EMVA 1288 Data Sheet m0550

This datasheet describes the specification according to the standard 1288 for “Characterization and Presentation of Specification Data for Image Sensors and Cameras of the European Machine Vision Association (EMVA)” (see www.standard1288.org or the *Zenodo EMVA 1288 community*). The measurements were performed with the AEON ACC2b RGB-IR, Release 3, 08.09.2014, SN 0012(). The performance parameters and estimated accuracy of the measurements are described in the technical report for the instrument, its calibration in the corresponding calibration report.

Measurements performed by B Jähne, HCI, Heidelberg University and H Herrmann, AEON

Vendor	PCO
Model	edge
Serial number	61000057
Sensor diagonal	21.77 mm
Lens category	Nikon F
Resolution	2560 × 2160, 16 bit
Pixel size	6.50 μm × 6.50 μm
Sensor type	CMOS
Shutter type	Rolling
Overlap capabilities	Overlapping
Maximum frame rate	30.4 Hz
Interface type	USB 3.0

Type of data presented	Single
Operation point 1, (page 6)	
Wavelength centroid	466.7 nm
Wavelength FWHM	19.8 nm
Gain, offset	default
Operation point 2, (page 21)	
Wavelength centroid	532.0 nm
Wavelength FWHM	30.5 nm
Gain, offset	default
Operation point 3, (page 36)	
Wavelength centroid	629.2 nm
Wavelength FWHM	13.0 nm
Gain, offset	default
Operation point 4, (page 51)	
Wavelength centroid	845.7 nm
Wavelength FWHM	21.1 nm
Gain, offset	default
Optional data measured	
None	

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 1

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure time	30.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.1°C
Frame rate	30.4 Hz	Camera temperature	29.2°C
Data transfer mode	Slow scan, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	467 nm, 19.8 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.455
Gain	
K (DN/e)	2.435
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.411
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	3.74
σ_d (e)	1.5
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	0.60
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	0.25
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	163
SNR _{max} (dB)	44.2
SNR _{max} (bits)	7.3
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	0.61
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	0.391
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.48
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	4.65
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	0.1100
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	2.12
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	58299
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	1380
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	26538
Dynamic range	
DR	12541
DR (dB)	82.0
DR (bit)	13.6
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	0.57
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	0.23
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	0.40

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 2

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure time	30.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.1°C
Frame rate	30.4 Hz	Camera temperature	29.2°C
Data transfer mode	Slow scan, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	532 nm, 30.5 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.545
Gain	
K (DN/e)	2.392
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.418
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	3.74
σ_d (e)	1.6
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	0.60
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	0.25
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	164
SNR _{max} (dB)	44.3
SNR _{max} (bits)	7.4
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	0.61
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	0.541
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.47
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	3.93
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	0.0931
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	2.14
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	49077
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	1162
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	26741
Dynamic range	
DR	12476
DR (dB)	81.9
DR (bit)	13.6
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	—

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 3

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure time	30.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.1°C
Frame rate	30.4 Hz	Camera temperature	29.2°C
Data transfer mode	Slow scan, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	629 nm, 13.0 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.553
Gain	
K (DN/e)	2.366
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.423
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	3.75
σ_d (e)	1.6
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	0.60
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	0.25
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	164
SNR _{max} (dB)	44.3
SNR _{max} (bits)	7.4
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	0.61
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	0.741
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.45
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	3.91
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	0.0925
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	2.16
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	48719
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	1153
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	26961
Dynamic range	
DR	12472
DR (dB)	81.9
DR (bit)	13.6
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	—

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 4

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure time	30.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.1°C
Frame rate	30.4 Hz	Camera temperature	29.2°C
Data transfer mode	Slow scan, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	846 nm, 21.1 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.209
Gain	
K (DN/e)	2.344
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.427
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	3.73
σ_d (e)	1.6
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	0.60
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	0.26
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	165
SNR _{max} (dB)	44.3
SNR _{max} (bits)	7.4
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	0.61
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	0.875
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.39
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	10.38
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	0.2458
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	2.17
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	130141
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	3080
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	27181
Dynamic range	
DR	12533
DR (dB)	82.0
DR (bit)	13.6
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	—

Detailed Data Operating Point 1, 467 nm

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1.1 Short-Time Stability (in extension of EMVA 1288)

Time series of mean value of dark image. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of irradiation at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of mean value of response at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

1.2 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.132	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.101
-0.005	-0.006	-0.029	-0.030	-0.029	-0.029	-0.030	-0.029	-0.029
-0.001	-0.002	-0.002	-0.003	-0.003	-0.002	-0.002	-0.002	-0.002
0.008	0.009	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.009	0.009	0.008
-0.012	-0.013	-0.013	-0.013	-0.013	-0.013	-0.014	-0.013	-0.013
0.012	0.012	0.012	0.011	0.011	0.012	0.011	0.012	0.012
-0.005	-0.006	-0.006	-0.006	-0.006	-0.006	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005
-0.004	-0.005	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.005	-0.004	-0.005	-0.005
0.012	0.011	0.011	0.012	0.011	0.011	0.012	0.012	0.012

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.013	0.009	0.008	0.009	0.008	0.009	0.008	0.008
-0.003	-0.001	-0.002	-0.001	-0.001	-0.002	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001
-0.003	-0.001	-0.002	-0.003	-0.002	-0.002	-0.003	-0.002	-0.002
0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.002
-0.001	-0.002	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000
0.003	0.001	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001

1.3 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

1.4 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

1.5 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

1.6 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 97.1 - 100.7 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.2\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0550, 467nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0550, 467nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Detailed Data Operating Point 2, 532 nm

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2.1 Short-Time Stability (in extension of EMVA 1288)

Time series of mean value of dark image. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of irradiation at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of mean value of response at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

2.2 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.133	0.104	0.103	0.103	0.103	0.102	0.102	0.103
-0.006	-0.006	-0.030	-0.030	-0.031	-0.030	-0.031	-0.031	-0.030
0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.001	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.011	0.011	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.010
-0.011	-0.011	-0.011	-0.011	-0.011	-0.010	-0.011	-0.011	-0.011
0.008	0.008	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.008	0.008	0.008
-0.008	-0.008	-0.008	-0.009	-0.009	-0.009	-0.009	-0.008	-0.009
-0.002	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.004	-0.003
0.017	0.016	0.017	0.016	0.016	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.016

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.014	0.007	0.005	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.007
0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.001	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
-0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.000
-0.000	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.000
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.002
-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001	-0.000	0.001	0.000	-0.000
-0.001	0.000	-0.001	-0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	-0.000

2.3 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

2.4 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

2.5 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

2.6 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 97.1 - 100.7 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.6\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0550, 532nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0550, 532nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Detailed Data Operating Point 3, 629 nm

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3.1 Short-Time Stability (in extension of EMVA 1288)

Time series of mean value of dark image. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of irradiation at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of mean value of response at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

3.2 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.134	0.105	0.104	0.105	0.104	0.104	0.105	0.105
-0.007	-0.008	-0.031	-0.031	-0.031	-0.031	-0.031	-0.031	-0.031
-0.002	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003
0.008	0.007	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.007
-0.009	-0.009	-0.009	-0.009	-0.008	-0.009	-0.009	-0.009	-0.009
0.015	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014
-0.011	-0.012	-0.012	-0.012	-0.012	-0.011	-0.012	-0.012	-0.012
-0.004	-0.005	-0.006	-0.006	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005
0.019	0.018	0.018	0.018	0.017	0.019	0.018	0.018	0.018

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.017	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.006
0.003	0.002	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002
0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001
-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000

3.3 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

3.4 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

3.5 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

3.6 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 97.1 - 100.7 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 2.2\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0550, 629nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0550, 629nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Detailed Data Operating Point 4, 846 nm

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4.1 Short-Time Stability (in extension of EMVA 1288)

Time series of mean value of dark image. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of irradiation at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

Time series of mean value of response at about 50% saturation. Vertical range: ± 1.5 temporal standard deviation.

4.2 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.125	0.096	0.095	0.094	0.095	0.095	0.095	0.096
-0.004	-0.005	-0.028	-0.029	-0.029	-0.029	-0.029	-0.029	-0.028
0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.005	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
-0.011	-0.010	-0.011	-0.010	-0.010	-0.011	-0.012	-0.011	-0.011
0.013	0.013	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.013	0.013	0.012	0.013
-0.008	-0.009	-0.009	-0.009	-0.008	-0.009	-0.009	-0.008	-0.008
-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.005	-0.005	-0.004
0.015	0.015	0.015	0.014	0.015	0.014	0.015	0.015	0.015

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.020	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.008
0.004	0.004	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	-0.001	0.001
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001
-0.001	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.001	-0.000
0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002
0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	-0.000
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.000	0.000	0.001
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002

4.3 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

4.4 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

4.5 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

4.6 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 97.1 - 100.7 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 2.6\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0550, 846nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0550, 846nm, 02.11.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Dark Current

Mean of dark signal versus exposure time.

Variance of dark signal versus exposure time.

Spatial variation of dark current (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e⁻/s from mean values

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e⁻/s from variance

Comments